

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Gbate**FIRST NAME:** Cyrille Jean Noël**PROGRAM CODE:** DILT**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 06**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied X US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author X did did *not* use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR ALL COURSE MATERIAL

1. Which of the following four answers refers to plagiarism?

- Don't take someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper with your name and give it to your professor would be plagiarism.
- Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you, putting your name on it, and giving it to your professor would be plagiarism.¹**
- Taking someone else's words or ideas, such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper with your name and give it to your professor would be plagiarism.
- You are helping someone to develop and write a dissertation so that you can put your name.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401D Coursepack Period 1*, 3rd ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 5.

2. What are the tertiary sources of research?
- Tertiary sources are books and articles that synthesize secondary sources for general readers. They include textbooks, encyclopedias (including Wikipedia), dictionaries, and articles in publications for broad audiences, like Time and the Atlantic. In the early stages of research, you can use tertiary sources to get a broad overview of your topic.²**
 - Tertiary sources are “original” materials to provide the “raw” data or evidence you will use to develop, test, and ultimately justify your hypothesis or claim.
 - Tertiary sources are usually the texts you analyze your data and the words on the page. In social sciences, such as sociology or political science, census or survey data would also count as primary sources, as would data obtained through observation or experiment in many fields.
 - Tertiary sources are books, articles, papers, or reports based on primary sources intended for scholarly or professional audiences.
3. What are the different parts of an elevator story?
- An elevator story has three parts: a problem statement highlighting an answer to So what, a sketch of your claim and major reasons, and a summary of your most important evidence.³**
 - An elevator story has three parts: a problem statement highlighting an answer to So what, a sketch of your claim and principal reasons, and all the details you need to understand the study.
 - An elevator story has four parts: a problem statement highlighting an answer to So what, a sketch of your claim and principal reasons, all the details you need to understand the study, and a summary of your most important evidence.
 - An elevator story has two parts: a sketch of your claim and principal reasons and a summary of your most important evidence.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual from Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 37.

³ *Ibid.*, 134.

4. How do you signal the notes-style citations in the sentence?
- In "notes" style quotes, you indicate that you have used a source by putting the page number in brackets at the end of the sentence in which you quote or refer to it.
 - In "notes" style quotations, you indicate that you have used a source by placing the author's name at the end of the sentence to which you quote to refer.
 - In "notes" style quotations, you indicate that you have used a source by placing a semicolon at the end of the sentence to which you quote to refer.
 - In notes-style citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a superscript number at the end of the sentence to which you quote it or refer.⁴**
5. How to signal Author-Date Style in the sentence?
- In author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference.⁵**
 - In author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author and date).
 - In author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a parenthetical citation (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) in the footnotes.
 - In author-date citations, you signal that you have used a source by placing a citation without parenthetical (including author, date, and relevant page numbers) next to your reference to it.
6. What is the best format to cite an electronic book?
- Janet M. Davis, *The Gospel of Kindness: Animal Welfare and the Making of Modern America* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016), 144–45, <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199733156.001.0001>.⁶**

⁴ Ibid., 141.

⁵ Ibid., 142.

⁶ Ibid., 189.

- M. Davis Janet, *The Gospel of Kindness: Animal Welfare and the Making of Modern America* <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199733156.001.0001.144-45>. (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016).
- M. Davis Janet. 2016, *The Gospel of Kindness: Animal Welfare and the Making of Modern America* <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199733156.001.0001.144-45>. (Oxford: Oxford University Press).
- Janet M. Davis, *The Gospel of Kindness: Animal Welfare and the Making of Modern America* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016), <https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780199733156.001.0001>, 144-145

7. What are the five basic components that include a full case citation?

- A full case citation includes five basic components: (1) the name of the case; (2) the published source in which the case may be found; (3) a parenthetical indicating the court and year of the decision; (4) other parenthetical information, if any; and (5) the subsequent history of the case, if any.⁷**
- A full case citation includes five components: the name of the case, the published source in the case found, a parenthetical indicating the court and year of the decision, other parenthetical information, if any, and the name of judges, if any.
- A full case citation includes five components: the name of the town, the published source in which the case was found, a parenthetical indicating the court and year of the decision, other parenthetical information, if any, and the name of judges, if any.
- A full case citation includes five components: the name of the town, the published source in which the case was found, a parenthetical indicating the court and year of the decision, other parenthetical information, if any, and the name of juries, if any.

8. What are the three basic elements of full citation to a federal statute include?

- The official name of the act; the published source in which the act may be found; and a parenthetical indicating either (i) the year the source was**

⁷ Mary Miles Prince, *The BLUE BOOK: A Uniform System of Citation*, Nineteenth edition (Massachusetts: The Harvard Law Review, 2010), 7.

published (used for code citations), or (ii) the year the statute was passed (used for citations to session laws).⁸

- The unofficial name of the act, the published source of the act, and a parenthetical indicating the year the source was published.
- The official name of the act and a parenthetical indicating the year the source was published and the year the statute was passed.
- The official name of the act, the published source in which the act founded the auteur's name, and a parenthetical indicating the year the source was published and the year the statute was passed.

⁸ Ibid., 15.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual from Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers. Revised. Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.